

Advanced polymer nanofibers for the online extraction coupled with liquid chromatography for the determination of emerging fluorinated contaminants in surface water

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ABSTRACT

Advanced polyacrylonitrile, polypropylene, polyhydroxybutyrate, polycaprolactone, and poly(vinylidene difluoride) nanofibers, including composite materials containing carbon nanoparticle additives, combined micro/nanofibers, and modified nanofibers with polyhydroxy coatings were filled into a cartridge and tested for the online solid phase extraction (SPE) of highly lipophilic and fluorinated organic contaminants. The reusable nanofiber-packed cartridge was coupled to an HPLC column to separate the analytes after direct elution. Electrospun poly(vinylidene difluoride) nanofibers embedded in a meltblown microfibrillar polycaprolactone scaffold were sufficiently robust in a high-pressure SPE-HPLC system and the most efficient adsorbent for the selective extraction of fluorinated pesticides. The optimized and validated online solid-phase extraction method coupled with chromatographic separation demonstrated an excellent trueness of 93–108 % and precision of better than 3.2 % RSD with six replicates. The entire analysis run took only 7 min, including the preconcentration step with the direct application of a 200 μ L sample volume. Since the method is fully automated, it significantly reduces time, solvent consumption, and the occurrence of human error. Our study highlights the potential of polymer nanofiber sorbents for the efficient environmental monitoring of emerging fluorinated contaminants and demonstrates a reliable, fully automated method for their determination.

1. Introduction

Sample pretreatment is a critical part of trace analysis. It is required to extract and preconcentrate target analytes as well as to remove interferences in complex matrices. Solid phase extraction (SPE) is the preferred method because it can handle different sample sizes, has high extraction yields, can process large sample volumes, enables selective enrichment using various sorbent chemistries, reduces solvent consumption, and has the potential for automation [1,2].

Nanomaterial-based sorbents have large surface areas that facilitate interactions and adsorption, allowing for rapid and efficient extraction [3,4]. In particular, polymer nanofibers are affordable, customizable, robust, and easily prepared materials. Typical polymers used to prepare nanofibers, usually by electrospinning, include polystyrene, polyacrylonitrile, and polyamides. Today, this portfolio is expanding to

include biodegradable and thermally stable polymers, as well as numerous types of composite materials that combine different chemistries and fiber types in a single sorbent. In addition, functionalizing and coating of fibers further improve their extraction properties [5–7].

Most of the common polymers provide mainly hydrophobic interactions, which are affected by hydrocarbon chain length, polar functional groups content, the presence of aromatic rings, and/or electronegative halogens in the monomer structure. The chemical composition affects the material final lipophilicity and selectivity toward target analytes, hydrophilicity, and water wettability, the latter of which is important for handling aqueous samples [6,8]. Nanomaterials play an important role in wastewater treatment and purification as efficient adsorbents of organic pollutants [3,9,10]. Nanofibers represent an alternative to particulate formats, which are more often used for extracting emerging organic contaminants, preconcentrating them from

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environmental matrices, and removing them [5,8].

Organochlorine compounds were once popular pesticides. However, most of them have been banned since the 1970s due to their toxicity and persistence in the environment. Examples include dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), aldrin, and heptachlor. More recently, endosulfan was banned as well. In the last decades, significant developments have occurred in the field of fluorinated compounds [11,12]. Fluorination appears to be more promising due to the high stability of the molecules, lipophilicity, pesticide selectivity and potency, prolonged residual activity, and biokinetics of the molecules. However, they have several disadvantages, such as poor degradability with long degradation times, a tendency to accumulate in living organisms, and persistence in the environment [12,13]. Although fluorinated pesticides are highly effective, they pose an equal risk and concern due to their content of at least one perfluorinated methyl group. Examples include trifluralin, oxyfluorfen, hexaflumuron, and fipronil. These pesticides are similar to “forever chemicals”, perfluoroalkylated substances, which are currently a great public concern due to their ubiquity, organotoxicity, immunotoxicity, and endocrine disruption [11].

As previously demonstrated, the moderately lipophilic compounds with a log P of about 3–4 show a good retentivity on the polymer nanofibers [6,14]. Our targets are the highly lipophilic and fluorinated organic pesticides shown in Fig. 1. Our goal is to select a fibrous sorbent with high selectivity for these emerging environmental pollutants to allow for their sensitive detection and removal from the environment. In this study, we test advanced nanofibrous sorbents prepared from various polymers, some of which contain carbon additives or a functionalized surface. We then compare them with respect to their selectivity toward fluorinated compounds. The effectiveness of the nanofiber sorbents is also compared to that of a common lipophilic octadecyl sorbent in particulate format. These materials are then used for an online SPE-HPLC system to achieve a fast and fully automated analysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

All the standards were of analytical grade. Hexaflumuron (HFM) was purchased from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). Lufenuron (LFN) and chlorfluazuron (CFZ) were obtained from Riedel-de Haën (Honeywell, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA). Terbutylazine (TAZ), terbutryn (TYN), oxyfluorfen (OFF), and trifluralin (TFN) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer GmbH (Augsburg, Germany). Stock solutions were

prepared in acetonitrile at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and stored at 4 °C. River water was sampled from the Labe River in Hradec Králové (Czech Republic) in November 2023.

2.2. Instrumentation and software

The online SPE-HPLC method was developed using the chromatographic system Shimadzu Prominence (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with an LC-20 ADP dual pump module, a DGU-20 A3 degassing unit, a SIL-20A autosampler, a CTO-20AC column oven with six-port selection valve, a CBM-20A communication module, and an SPD-M20A diode array detector. Data acquisition during chromatographic analyses and their evaluations were performed using Lab Solution software (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan).

The analytical columns tested for selectivity and resolution were Ascentis Express C18 (50 × 2.1 mm, particle size 2.7 μm), Ascentis Express F5 (100 × 4.6 mm, particle size 2.7 μm) from Supelco, Kinetex Phenyl-Hexyl (50 × 2.1 mm, particle size 5 μm), Kinetex PFP (50 × 4.6 mm, particle size 2.6 μm), Kinetex C18 EVO (50 × 4.6 mm, particle size 2.6 μm), and Onyx Monolithic C18 (50 × 4.6 mm) from Phenomenex, and Accucore RP-MS (100 × 2.1 mm, particle size 2.6 μm) from Thermo Scientific. A Kinetex C18 EVO analytical column was selected for the final chromatographic separations. Online extraction was carried out using polymer nanofibers packed in a stainless-steel cartridge (10 × 4.0 mm ID) and the extraction efficiency was compared to that of a SecurityGuard cartridge (4 × 2.0 mm ID, Phenomenex) packed with conventional C18 sorbent.

2.3. Polymer nanofiber sorbents

Polymer nanofibers were produced from polyacrylonitrile (PAN), polypropylene (PP), polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), poly(vinylidene difluoride) (PVDF), and polycaprolactone (PCL) via electrospinning of their solutions. Fibers from the thermoplastic polymers PP, PHB, and PCL were also prepared using melt blowing. The combination of both methods then allowed for the preparation of PCL/PVDF composite fibers. Hybrid PCL fibers filled with carbon nanofillers including graphene (G), activated carbon (AC), and carbon black (CB) were selected for their potentially enhanced hydrophobic interactions and larger surface area resulting from the higher roughness of these fibers [6]. High carbon loading was achieved by alternating current electrospinning [6]. PCL fibers were also dip-coated with the polyhydroxy compounds dopamine (D), heparin (HEP), hesperidin (HES), and tannin (TAN), and with

Fig. 1. Structures and log P values of lipophilic and fluorinated pesticides used in this study.

graphene oxide (GO) to modify the fiber surface chemistry and to increase water wettability for good contact with aqueous samples [14]. The list of the tested polymer nanofibers is summarized in Table 1.

The preparation and modifications of the nanofibers were carried out at the Technical University of Liberec, their description is presented in our recent review [6]. Detailed information on their composition, technical parameters for fabrication, and characterization is available in the Supplementary material.

2.4. Preparation of the nanofiber-packed extraction cartridge

Dry polymer nanofiber sheets were evenly loaded into a stainless-steel cartridge, as shown in Fig. 2, and manually compressed to avoid void volumes. The cartridge was then rinsed with methanol for a few minutes, and several blank online SPE-HPLC runs were carried out with methanol injection only to wash and equilibrate the extraction sorbent. Finally, extractions of a standard solution were performed. Back pressure and analyte peak symmetry were monitored to verify good cartridge packing. After each run, the extraction cartridge and the analytical column were washed with an organic solvent.

2.5. Online SPE-HPLC method

The extraction cartridge was installed in the loop of a six-port valve upstream of the separation column of the HPLC system. The column switching system was programmed to first load a 200 μ L sample onto a nanofiber-packed extraction cartridge, followed by a clean-up step with an aqueous mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min for 0.5–1 min, depending on the sorbent. Following extraction, the valve switched and directed an elution mobile phase in backflush mode from the extraction cartridge to the Kinetex C18 EVO separation column. The initial mobile phase composition of 80:20 methanol/water increased in a gradient program to 100 % methanol, allowing complete elution from the extraction cartridge and simultaneous separation on the analytical column using a gradient program. The optimized gradient held the initial 80:20 methanol/water composition for 1.5 min, ramped linearly to 90 % methanol in 2.5 min, and then to 100 % methanol in 1 min. After holding at 100 % methanol for 0.5 min, the composition was switched to the initial conditions, and the system was equilibrated for 1.4 min. The total analysis time, including the online extraction step and chromatographic separation, was 7 min. All pesticides were detected by UV absorption at 220 nm.

Table 1

List of used polymers and functionalization agents with their acronyms.

Fibers	Polymers	Functionalization	Functionalization agent
PHB	Poly-3-hydroxybutyrate		
PP	Polypropylene Isotactic		
PAN	Polycaprolactone		
PCL	Polycaprolactone		
PCL:G (10:1)	Polycaprolactone	Particles in mass	Graphene
PCL:CB	Polycaprolactone	Particles in mass	Carbon black
PCL:AC	Polycaprolactone	Particles in mass	Activated carbon
μ PCL/ nPVDF	PCL/Poly(vinylidene difluoride)	Composite fibers	
μ PCL/ nPCL	Polycaprolactone/ Polycaprolactone	Composite fibers	
+TAN		Surface coating	Tannin
+HES		Surface coating	Hesperidin
+DOP		Surface coating	Dopamine
+DOP		Surface coating	Dopamine +
+H		Surface coating	Heparin
+GO		Surface coating	Graphene oxide

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Selectivity of the nanofiber sorbents

In this project, we focused on the extraction and separation of lipophilic and fluorinated organic contaminants using an online SPE-HPLC setup. These contaminants were represented by the benzoylurea pesticides chlorfluazuron, hexaflumuron, and lufenuron, the fluorinated herbicides trifluralin and oxyfluorfen, and as a reference the triazine herbicides terbuthryn and terbuthylazine, which have moderate lipophilicity. The latter two herbicides with log P values of 3–4 have already been reported as ideal targets for extraction using polymer nanofibers [6,14].

For the column-switching online SPE-HPLC setup, the nanofiber-packed extraction cartridge was connected to the HPLC via a six-port switching valve. First, it was percolated with the sample and then with the aqueous washing mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min for 30 s. The lowest washing volume of the SPE sorbent after sample application was chosen to minimize analyte loss. The retained analytes were eluted to the analytical column in a gradient of the mobile phase containing an increasing percentage of methanol. Backflush elution from the extraction cartridge to the analytical column significantly improved peak shapes by focusing the elution zone, especially for analytes with higher retention.

Different polymer nanofibers were tested and compared for the extraction of target analytes in terms of selectivity. They ranged from very hydrophobic polyolefin PP, polyester PCL, and its composite with fluorine-containing PVDF nanofibers, to more water-wettable polar polymers PHB and PAN. Extraction efficiency was expressed as the relative recovery compared to the reference particulate C18 reversed phase sorbent. As expected, triazine herbicides generally exhibited good retention on all the sorbents, except for only 60 % terbuthylazine recovery using the PAN fibers (Fig. 3). In contrast, fluorinated compounds were only retained well on the PCL/PVDF composite and the PAN fibers, as also documented in Fig. 3.

We also tested various PCL fibers that were modified to affect their selectivity and surface area. According to our preliminary screening results reported elsewhere [14,15], polyphenolic surface coatings increased water wettability and increased the extraction efficiency of polar analytes. However, coating with compounds containing polyhydroxy functionalities, namely dopamine, heparin, hesperidin, and tannin, did not improve the retention of fluorinated pesticides. In contrast, graphene oxide coating resulted in two to three times higher recovery of fluorinated compounds compared to pure PCL nanofibers (Fig. S-1). The final materials tested were hybrid fibers with incorporated nanoparticle additives, including graphene, carbon black, and activated carbon. No additive leaking was observed after the first intensive washing of the sorbents, the analytical column did not suffer any clogging or back-pressure fluctuation. As shown in Fig. S-1, comparing the relative increase in recoveries to plain PCL nanofibers, the presence of activated carbon and carbon black in PCL significantly improved the recovery of fluorinated compounds. However, PCL with a graphene oxide coating or PCL/PVDF composite fibers produced even better results.

Fig. 4 shows that none of the simple polymer nanofibers provided recovery comparable to C18 for all analytes, relating to their selectivity and smaller surface area of nonporous fibers compared to the commercial porous particulate sorbent (see Table S-3 for details). The most promising PVDF nanofibers could not be used alone due to their limited mechanical stability under high pressure. In our previous study [16], we demonstrated the advantage of composite fibers, which benefit from combining polymers of different chemistries and two types of fibers, i.e., a robust meltblown microfiber scaffold and electrospun nanofibers, which increase the sorbent surface area. This approach solved the problem of PVDF nanofiber fragility and structural collapse under high pressure in the online SPE-HPLC system. It also provided a robust

Fig. 2. Preparation of a sealed cartridge for online SPE containing polymer nanofibers.

Fig. 3. Extraction recoveries of fluorinated pesticides using online SPE-HPLC setup with different polymer nanofibers compared to that of C18 sorbent. The relative standard deviations of three online SPE-HPLC measurements were less than 5 %.

Fig. 4. Relative extraction recoveries of different polymer nanofibers after extraction and washing with water in an online SPE-HPLC setup compared to particulate C18 sorbent set as 100 %. The relative standard deviations of three online SPE-HPLC measurements were less than 5 %.

sorbent with good selectivity. Based on the preliminary test results, PCL coated with graphene oxide and PCL/PVDF composite were selected for the final optimization of the online SPE-HPLC method.

3.2. Optimization of the online SPE-HPLC method

Optimizing the chromatographic method included selecting an analytical column to rapidly separate the analytes. We tested various stationary phases consisting of porous shell particles with C18, phenylhexyl, and pentafluorophenyl chemistries packed in 5–10 cm long columns to minimize back pressure in the system. The Kinetex EVO C18

column provided the best resolution of the analytes in the shortest time. All analytes featured neutral pKa and no pH adjustment of the mobile phase was necessary. Methanol was preferred over acetonitrile as part of the mobile phase due to its "greener" nature and better compatibility with polycaprolactone fibers, particularly since it dissolves in acetonitrile [16]. The column oven temperature was maintained at 20 °C to ensure consistent conditions every day and the stability of the PCL nanofiber cartridges. Finally, the gradient elution program was optimized, and the final separation is shown in Fig. 5. The gradient also included a final cleaning step with 100 % methanol and an equilibration step. Similar to commercial online SPE cartridges, our nanofiber-packed

Fig. 5. Separation of selected pesticides (5 mg/L) using the optimized method. Conditions: Analytical column Phenomenex Kinetex C18 EVO (50 × 4.6 mm, 2.6 μm particle size), gradient elution: 0–0.5 min 80:20 methanol/water, 0.5–3 min linear increase to 90 % methanol, 3–4 min ramp to 100 % methanol, 4–4.5 min held at 100 %, then returned to the initial conditions and equilibration for 1.5 min, flow rate 0.5 mL/min, injection volume 10 μL, UV detection at 220 nm.

cartridge could be used for more than fifty extraction cycles during method optimization and validation. Once packed, the extraction cartridge did not need to be replaced unless it became clogged, even with real matrix samples, as reported previously in various studies [6]. The sample volume was scaled up to 200 μL using the largest available sample loop to preconcentrate more sample for separation. No problems with overloading or worsening of the peak shape were observed. The river sample was injected directly, i.e., filtration was omitted as the analytes may retain on the filter and generate an error. In the case of crude particles and visible dirt, centrifugation of the samples is recommended.

We further optimized the extraction procedure using nanofibers with the best selectivity and recovery of the target analytes. Taking care to avoid analyte loss, we tested increasing in the percentage of the organic component in the aqueous washing mobile phase to achieve better cleanup from matrix interferences. A 30 s short wash of GO-coated PCL fibers with only 10 % aqueous MeOH allowed for interferences removal without analyte loss. However, the analytes strongly adsorbed on PCL/

PVDF fibers remained retained there even after 1 min wash with 20 % MeOH (Fig. S-2), which significantly reduced matrix interferences (Fig. S-3). PCL/PVDF composite fibers demonstrated the best selectivity and extraction efficiency as a fluorine-containing adsorbent for specific extraction of fluorine atom-containing compounds and exhibited great robustness in the high-pressure HPLC system.

3.3. Method validation

The optimized online SPE-HPLC method using PCL/PVDF composite nanofiber extraction cartridge for the determining emerging contaminants in river water was validated in terms of linearity, sensitivity, and accuracy as trueness and precision of the measurement. No analytes were detected in a blank river water, which was used for validation. Chromatograms of blank river water and its counterpart spiked with standards are shown in Fig. 6.

The linear range of the method was 5–1000 ng/mL, as was verified by matrix calibration at 8 concentration levels. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was set as the lowest point of the calibration plot and experimentally verified as preferable to estimation from the slope. The limit of detection (LOD) was 1.5 ng/mL for all analytes investigated, except oxyfluorfen, for which it was 3.0 ng/mL. These values were calculated from the ratios 10-fold and 3-fold signal-to-noise for LOQ and LOD, respectively. Six samples were spiked at 50 ng/mL and analyzed, their concentrations were calculated using matrix calibration and plotted against the theoretical spiked concentrations to evaluate method trueness. The results showed excellent method precision due to the programmed online SPE step, with the trueness ranging from 92.7 to 108.3 % with RSD less than 3.2 %. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Reproducibility between individual SPE column packings was 5–19 % expressed as RSD from peak areas; however, a column once packed can be used for hundreds of cycles in our experience [6,16], hence the demand for batch-to-batch reproducibility is reduced.

3.4. Comparison with other extraction protocols

Table 3 lists recent solid phase extraction methods combined with liquid chromatography separation that were designed to determine fluorinated contaminants. MS/MS detection is generally required to yield higher sensitivity, but this study is focused mainly on testing new

Fig. 6. HPLC separations of blank river water (blue line) and river water spiked with 100 ng/mL of the target pesticides after online extraction (black line) using composite PCL/PVDF nanofibers. Conditions: Analytical column Phenomenex Kinetex C18 EVO (50 × 4.6 mm, 2.6 μm particle size), extraction: 20 % MeOH for 1 min; gradient elution: 0–1.5 min 80:20 methanol/water, 1.5–4 min linear increase to 90 % methanol, 4–5 min ramp to 100 % methanol, 5–5.6 min held at 100 %, then return to the initial conditions and equilibration for 1.4 min, flow rate 0.5 mL/min, injection volume 200 μL, UV detection at 220 nm. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 2

Validation parameters of the online SPE-HPLC method for the determination of pesticides in surface water using PCL/PVDF nanofibers.

	Linear range (ng/mL)	Calibration plot y = kx + d	Correlation coefficient	LOD (ng/mL)	Spike concentration (ng/mL)	Calculated concentration (ng/mL ± SD)	Trueness (%)	Precision RSD in % (n = 6)
Terbuthylazine	5–1000	1389x - 11648	0.9997	1.5	50.0	46.4 ± 0.5	92.7	1.1
Terbutryn	5–1000	1354x - 322	0.9999	1.5	50.0	47.5 ± 0.6	95.1	1.3
Hexaflumuron	5–1000	342x - 9791	0.9936	1.5	50.0	54.1 ± 1.0	108.3	1.9
Oxyfluorfen	10–1000	228x - 5887	0.9940	3.0	50.0	53.9 ± 1.0	107.8	1.8
Lufenuron	5–1000	362x - 10210	0.9953	1.5	50.0	53.0 ± 1.1	106.0	2.1
Trifluralin	5–1000	157x - 2308	0.9969	1.5	50.0	46.9 ± 0.8	93.7	1.8
Chlorfluazuron	5–1000	410x - 9904	0.9970	1.5	50.0	52.9 ± 1.7	105.8	3.2

Table 3

LC methods designed for the determination of fluorinated contaminants using SPE step for their clean-up and preconcentration.

Sample pretreatment	Sorbent	Extraction time ^a	Desorption from the sorbent	Analytes	Sample	Analytical performance (LOD µg L ⁻¹)	Analytical method	
SPE	TiO ₂ @MOF-919(Fe-Cu)	20 min	1 mL MeOH	benzoylurea pesticides	water and juice (diluted 2x) 10 mL	LOD 0.4–0.6 Recovery 72.3–108.4 % RSD 1.8–3.2 %	LC-UV 14 min	[20]
SPE	Florisil (activated magnesium silicate) and activated carbon	30 min LLE extraction/40 min SPE	30 mL ACN/toluene (v/v = 1:3)	benzoylurea pesticides	tea 2 g to 10 mL ACN	LOD 0.03–1.0 Recovery 90.4–103.0 % RSD 2.1–4.0 %	LC-MS 7 min	[21]
QuEChERS	C18, graphitized carbon black, PSA (N-propyl ethylenediamine)	11 min	collected supernatant (MeOH)	perfluorinated compounds (PFOS, PFOA)	edible oils 2 g to 10 mL MeOH (1 % ammonia)	LOD 0.03–0.1 94.4–109.0 % RSD 2.3–7.2 %	LC-MS 15 min	[22]
MI-FPSE	Cellulose coated with the sol-gel CW 20 M	40 min adsorption/2 min desorption + evaporation	1 mL MeOH	benzoylurea pesticides	environmental water 100 mL	LOD 0.06 Recovery 94.0–107.0 % RSD 1.4–6.1 %	LC-UV 10 min	[24]
MMF-SPME	MAED monolith	70 min adsorption/15 min desorption + evaporation	400 µl ACN	benzoylurea pesticides	water and juice (diluted 10x) 20 mL	LOD 0.03–0.3 Recovery 65.1–118.0 % RSD 0.8–9.8 %	LC-UV 12 min	[23]
MMF-SPME	Highly fluorinated monolith	50 min adsorption/20 min desorption	400 µl ACN/TFA, v/v = 99/1	fluorobenzenes	environmental water 20 mL	LOD 1.1–5.9 Recovery 80.2–112.0 % RSD 4.2–10.6 %	LC-UV 25 min	[19]
mSPE	magnetic fluorinated COF	15 min adsorption/15 min desorption + evaporation	1.5 mL MeOH	perfluorinated compounds	milk (1000x diluted) 20 mL	LOD 0.005–0.05 Recovery 81.3–128.1 % RSD 0.5–11.8 %	LC-MS 20 min	[18]
mSPE	magnetic fluorinated COF	5 min adsorption/5 min desorption + evaporation	5 mL MeOH	benzoylurea pesticides	wine and juice 25 mL	LOD 0.4–4.0 Recovery 84.1–110.0 % RSD 0.7–10.0 %	LC-MS 7 min	[17]
Our online SPE	PCL/PVDF nanofibers	1 min	LC mobile phase	perfluorinated pesticides	environmental water 200 µL	LOD 1.5–3.0 Recovery 92.7–108.3 % RSD 1.1–3.2 %	LC-UV 6 min	This study

COF – covalent-organic framework, LOD – limit of detection, MAED - poly(methacrylic acid-co-ethylene dimethacrylate), MI-FPSE – magnet integrated fabric phase sorptive extraction, MOF – metal-organic framework, MMF-SPME - multiple monolithic fiber solid-phase microextraction, mSPE – magnetic solid phase extraction, PCL/PVDF – polycaprolactone/poly(vinylidene difluoride).

^a Summed up reported time of adsorption/desorption, centrifugation, and flow rate of passing liquid, however, estimation of one extraction run could be higher due to transporting of the sample, pipetting, evaporation, reconstitution, etc.

sorbents and SPE method comparison.

Some of these reports also highlight the effectiveness of fluorinated adsorbents for selectively extracting fluorine-containing compounds [17–19]. Specifically, column-based SPE has been reported by Mei et al. and Chen et al. [20,21], dispersive formats in QuEChERS by Tu et al. [22], magnetically collected SPE by Xu et al. and Zhang et al. [17,18], solid-phase microextraction with monolithic fiber by Huang et al. and Mei et al. [19,23], and stirred fabric phase sorptive extraction by Manousi et al. [24]. Several novel sorbents, including metal-organic frameworks [20], covalent organic frameworks [17,18], and functionalized monoliths [19,23] have also been introduced. However, none of these approaches was used for online SPE-HPLC of fluorinated contaminants as our proposed fully automated method. The high

automation and sample throughput increase greenness of the procedure, since only 0.5 mL of 20 % MeOH in water is used for sample extraction, and the elution is carried out directly during chromatographic elution, saving solvents and resulting in a 7-min analysis only, including the extraction step. Notably, the nanofibrous sorbent is reusable. Evaluation using the AgreePrep software [25] is depicted in Fig. S-4 in the Supplementary material.

4. Conclusion

We tested advanced polymer nanofiber materials for extracting highly lipophilic and fluorinated organic contaminants using online SPE coupled to HPLC. Of the materials tested, the PCL/PVDF composite and

the graphene oxide-coated PCL fibers demonstrated superior selectivity and retention. This enabled rapid and efficient preconcentration and cleanup of the pesticides from river water. The PCL/PVDF composite fibers confirmed the effectiveness of the fluorinated adsorbents for the specific extraction of fluorine-containing compounds. Overcoming the fragility of electrospun PVDF fibers in a high-pressure HPLC system was achieved by producing a composite that embedded these nanofibers in robust PCL meltblown microfibers. This composite provided the necessary mechanical scaffold and porosity, allowing for lower flow resistance.

Several previous methods required manual handling, were slow, and took up to 30 min to complete [19,23,24]. Our approach includes an online SPE step, yields at least comparable or even better recoveries, requires only a 200 μL sample, and is completed in a significantly shorter time of only 7 min. The major advantage is the full automation of the entire extraction and separation processes, which minimizes sample handling and human error. This results in excellent inter-day repeatability, with an RSD of less than 3.2 % compared to 5–10 % reported by other groups. Our method eliminates the evaporation and reconstitution steps as well as sample transfer. In comparison to the common chromatography method where the sample injection volume is 5–10 μL , the increased injection volume of 200 μL in our on-line SPE method enables reaching the preconcentration factor values 20–40. The extract is eluted directly onto the analytical column, reducing organic solvent consumption.

We validated the resulting online SPE-HPLC method, which uses a PCL/PVDF nanofiber-packed extraction cartridge. Due to automation, the method showed excellent repeatability and accuracy in determining the target contaminants. The selected sorbents were stable under high pressure and reusable, thus making them a sustainable option for environmental contamination monitoring.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ivona Kolichová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jakub Erben:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Data curation. **Jan Vinter:** Investigation. **Dalibor Šatínský:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **František Švec:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Erwin Rosenberg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128810>.

Data availability statement

The original data used in this publication will be openly available in Zenodo under the <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018974>.

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